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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: *This article analyzes the economy of the Republics of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan, their specifics, the main macroeconomic indicators.*

Key words: *economy, macroeconomic indicators, specifics, historical features, ancient traditions.*

This year marks the 28th anniversary of the establishment of diplomatic relations between Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan. This date marks a period of dynamic development and enrichment of relations between the two countries with new content. Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan are important states of Central Asia. Relations between the two countries are consistently developing in the spirit of good-neighborliness and strategic partnership. These partnerships are based on the strong ties of friendship and brotherhood, the common history, language and culture of our peoples¹.

Mutually beneficial cooperation between our countries is characterized by a trusting and constructive dialogue. Over the past twenty-five years, a solid legal framework for cooperation between our states has been created. There are more than 200 legal acts related to various industries. These include the Treaty of eternal friendship between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Kazakhstan (1998), the treaty on strategic partnership (2013). They establish the basic foundation of bilateral relations, i.e. the principles of equality, mutual understanding, comprehensive cooperation and trust.²

Uzbekistan is Kazakhstan's largest trading partner in Central Asia. At the business forum held in Astana with the participation of the business circles of the two countries, trade agreements and investment agreements were signed for a total amount of about 1 billion US dollars. Today, the business structures of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan put forward a number of proposals for the creation of joint ventures, the opening of trading houses, and the implementation of promising and mutually

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kazakhstan%E2%80%93Uzbekistan_relations

² По данным Статкомитета СНГ (дата обращения 13.05.2020 / электронный источник www.cisstat.com)

beneficial investment projects. Specific goals have been set to bring the volume of mutual trade turnover between the two countries to 5 billion US dollars.

Another important area of cooperation — the accelerated integration of the transport infrastructures of Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan-will be crucial in the formation of transport and transit corridors and will create conditions for stimulating trade and investment in our countries, further developing bilateral and regional cooperation.

Since time immemorial, our countries have huge industrial and mineral resources, agricultural products, a large number of semi-finished products obtained in the process of processing, natural resources, and developed infrastructure capabilities. Modern exploration of the earth's interior is associated with the development of deposits rich in reserves of precious, non-ferrous and rare metals, various products of organic fuel, oil, natural gas and gas condensate, brown and semi-coke coals, shale fuel, uranium and many types of necessary raw materials for construction.

On the territory of Uzbekistan, a complex of minerals has been identified, containing about a hundred types of mineral raw materials, sixty of which are already used in the national economy.

It is confirmed that Uzbekistan holds a leading position in the reserves of such minerals as gold, uranium, copper, natural gas, tungsten, potassium salt, phosphorites, kaolin, not only among the CIS countries, but also around the world. In particular, it ranks fourth in the world in terms of gold reserves, seventh in terms of its production, eleventh in terms of copper reserves, eighth in terms of uranium reserves, and twelfth in terms of production.

Gold is a crucial commodity in providing the economy of our country with financial resources during the pandemic, increasing economic stability. In particular, the volume of gold exports of our country for October, November and December of the current year 2020 amounted to 5804.4 million dollars. This amounted to 38-38. 2% of the total volume of exported goods and services.

Table-1

LET'S ANALYZE THE ECONOMY OF KAZAKHSTAN.³

	Indicators	2019	2020	2021
	Population, at the end of the year, million people	18,6	18,9	19,2
	Working-age population, million people	9,2	9,3	9,4
	Average monthly nominal salary of an employee, USD	488	450	452
	Average monthly nominal salary of an employee in the national currency	186815	198760	203120
	Gross domestic product, billion US dollars United States National currency	181,7	184,8	190,4
	Gross domestic product, billion US dollarsUS national currency	69532,6	70342,7	72389,5
	GDP per capita, US dollars	9768,8	9777,8	9916,7
	GDP per capita, thousand national currency	3738,3	3721,8	3770,3
	Foreign trade turnover, billion US dollars US \$	97,8	98,5	99,4
0	Exports, billion US dollars US \$	58,1	58,7	59,1
1	Imports, billion US dollars	39,7	39,8	40,3

³ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/kazakhstan/overview>

Table-2
ANALYSIS OF THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN⁴

	Indicators	2019	2020	2021
	Population, at the end of the year, million people	33,9	34,1	34,3
	Working-age population, million people	14,9	15,1	15,3
	Average monthly nominal salary of an employee, USD	263,3	267,5	269,4
	Average monthly nominal salary of an employee in the national currency	2324	2350,7	2477,3
	Gross domestic product, billion US dollars United States National currency	57,9	58,2	58,9
	Gross domestic product, billion US dollars US national currency	511838,1	517789,8	523664,2
	GDP per capita, US dollars	1707,96	1706,74	1717,2
	GDP per capita, thousand national currency	15098,47	15184,45	15267,17
	Foreign trade turnover, billion US dollars US \$	35,9	36,8	37,1
0	Exports, billion US dollars US \$	14	14,9	15,1
1	Imports, billion US dollars	21,9	21,9	22,0

From the above tables, it can be seen that the Republic of Uzbekistan does not fully use its economic potential, given that it is twice as large as the Republic of Kazakhstan in terms of population, but 6 times smaller in terms of land area. This is one of the most important tasks facing our state for the radical transformation and development of the country's economy. The question arises, what kind of work should we do to achieve this? We believe that it is necessary to conduct an in-depth analysis and evaluate the following factors in a separate set.

1. Low competitive environment due to the high share of monopoly enterprises in our state
2. High level of cronyism and bribery among individuals in our country

⁴ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/uzbekistan/overview>

3. Hence the outflow of talented specialists to other developed countries
4. The development of the hidden economy in our country in comparison with other countries
5. The result is an increase in the number of entries in the accounting statements of enterprises

Given these circumstances, we would like to make the following proposals for the development of our country's economy:

1. For the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in certain areas, it is necessary to gradually reduce the share of the state in these areas
2. Maintaining the state's share, taking into account important aspects of strategically important enterprises and organizations
3. Creating a specific tourist route scheme to attract individual tourists and increase the tourist weight in our country
4. Develop and provide customers with visual travel routes taking into account the conditions of the pandemic in our country
5. Organization and development of "women's pilgrimage tourism" aimed at individual women in our country

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